

NATIONAL SKILL QUALIFICATION FRAMEWORK AND NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY NEP 2020

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Abstract

Our government of India launched the National Skills Qualifications Framework (NSQF) in December 2013 and was rationalized and notified in June, 2023. NSQF is an outcome and competency-based framework which organizes qualifications according to a series of levels of knowledge, skills, aptitude, and responsibility levels defined in terms of learning outcomes which the learner must acquire through formal, non-formal or informal learning which may comprise of academics, vocational education, training & skilling and experiential learning including relevant experience and proficiency or professional levels acquired, subject to assessment. The NSQF is segregated from Level 1 to 8, and each level represents a different level of skills, complexity, knowledge, responsibility and autonomy.

Key Words- *Skill Education, National Education, Competency, Experiential learning, Co-curricular and extracurricular activities etc.*

Key features of NSQF are as Below:

- i. Provide for integrating and creditizing vocational education, training and skill learning in various dimensions of academics, skilling and experiential learning including relevant experience and proficiency/ professional levels acquired, subject to assessment;

- ii. Clearly prescribe the desired competency levels in terms of knowledge, skills, aptitude, responsibility and learning outcomes expected after undergoing the course/ qualification while assigning a pre-defined NSQF/ NCrf level;
- iii. Facilitate assigning of credit levels across vocational education/ skilling including that in school and higher education, based on the cumulative numbers of hours/ years of learning;
- iv. Establish academic equivalence between vocational & general education while enabling mobility within & between them;
- v. Enable multi-disciplinarily, multiple entry-multiple exit (ME-ME) and progression pathways within and between school education, higher education, technical education, vocational education, training & skilling, and the job markets;
- vi. Provide flexibility for students/ learners to choose their learning trajectories and career choices, including option for mid-way course correction
- vii. Recognize learning through close partnership with industry and employers through internships apprenticeships and on the job training across all sectors;
- viii. Provide for Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL) through a credible assessment process;
- ix. NSQF enables and promotes lifelong learning and skill development.

Under the Govt of India's Skill India Mission (SIM), the Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship (MSDE) delivers skill, re-skill and up-skill training through an extensive network of skill development centres/colleges/institutes etc. under various schemes, viz. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY), Jan Shikshan Sansthan (JSS), National Apprenticeship Promotion Scheme (NAPS) and Craftsman Training Scheme (CTS) through Industrial Training Institutes (ITIs), to all the sections of the society, including youth, across the country. The brief of these schemes is as under:

Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY): PMKVY Scheme is for imparting skill development training through Short-Term Training (STT) and up-skilling and re-skilling through Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL) to youth across the country including rural areas.

Jan Shikshan Sansthan (JSS) Scheme: The main target of the JSS is to impart vocational skills to the non-literates, neo-literates and the persons having rudimentary level of education

and school dropouts upto 12th standard in the age group of 15-45 years, with due age relaxation in case of “Divyangjan” and other deserving cases. Priority is given to Women, SC, ST, OBC and Minorities in the rural areas and urban low-income areas.

National Apprenticeship Promotion Scheme (NAPS): This Scheme is for promoting apprenticeship training and increasing the engagement of apprentices by providing financial support for payment of stipend to apprentices. Training consists of Basic Training and On-the-Job Training / Practical Training at workplace in the industry.

Craftsmen Training Scheme (CTS): This scheme is for providing long-term training through Industrial Training Institutes (ITIs) across the country. The ITIs offer a range of vocational/skill training courses covering a large number of economic sectors with an objective to provide skilled workforce to the industry as well as self-employment of youth.

NSQF Courses

NSQF is a nationally integrated education and competency-based framework that enables persons to acquire desired competency levels. The National Skills Qualifications Framework (NSQF) organizes qualifications according to a series of levels of knowledge, skills and aptitude. These levels, graded from one to ten, are defined in terms of learning outcomes which the learner must possess regardless of whether they were acquired through formal, non-formal or informal learning. It is, therefore, a nationally integrated education and competency-based skill and quality assurance framework that will provide for multiple pathways, horizontal as well as vertical, including vocational education, vocational training, general education and technical education, thus linking one level of learning to another higher level. This will enable a person to acquire desired competency levels, transit to the job market and at an opportune time, return for acquiring additional skills to further upgrade their competencies. NSQF in India was notified on 27th December 2013.

Background of development of skill qualification framework in India

Through the National Policy on Skill Development, 2009, India recognized the need for the development of a national qualification framework that would transcend general education as well as vocational education and training. The Policy envisioned that the framework would stimulate and support reforms in skills development and facilitate establishment of nationally standardized, acceptable, and internationally comparable qualifications. In the absence of an organization at the Central level to develop such a framework, individual Ministries started

working on development of the framework, which were to subsequently be subsumed in the National framework, when available. Accordingly, the Ministry of Labour and Employment developed the National Vocational Qualifications Framework (NVQF) and the Ministry of Human Resource Development developed the National Vocational Education Qualification Framework (NVEQF).

Realizing the need for a unified framework, an Inter-Ministerial Committee was formed by the Cabinet Secretariat to utilize the work already done by the two Ministries as the foundation of the National Skills Qualification Framework (NSQF) notified vide notification no.8/6/2013-Invt dated 27th December, 2013 by the Department of Economic Affairs, Ministry of Finance Prior to this, the National Skill Development Agency was notified in June 2013 by the Department of Economic Affairs with a mandate to anchor and operationalize the National Skill Qualification Framework (NSQF) to ensure that quality and standards meet sector specific requirements.

Establishment of National Council for Vocational Education and Training (NCVET):

The National Council for Vocational Education and Training (NCVET) was notified on 5th December 2018, vide notification no. No. SD-17/113/2017 E&PW, with the approval of the Cabinet dated 10th October 2018, subsuming Page 4 of 40 the erstwhile National Skill Development Agency (NSDA) and the National Council of Vocational Training (NCVT).

The National Council for Vocational Education and Training has been entrusted with the development, qualitative improvement and regulation of vocational education and training, for granting recognition to and monitoring the functioning of awarding bodies, assessment agencies, skill information providers, and training bodies, and to perform other incidental functions as specified in the notification. The establishment of NCVET has also consolidated the fragmented regulatory framework in the Vocational Education and Training (VET) and skill ecosystem.

Conclusion

The National Education Policy, 2020 has been launched by the Government of India in July 2020. The policy lays emphasis on making the education more holistic and effective by integration of general (academic) and vocational education while ensuring the vertical and horizontal mobility of students and learners between academic and vocational streams. The NEP 2020, emphasizes upon removing hard distinction between arts, science and commerce; and between curricular, co-curricular and extracurricular activities; and between vocational

and general education. NEP focuses on flexible curricular structure and multidisciplinary learning. Whereas National Credit Framework (NCrF) is meant to fulfill the vision of National Education Policy 2020, a National Credit Framework (NCrF) has been approved by the government which is a comprehensive credit framework encompassing elementary, school, higher, and vocational education & training. NCrF focuses on making education more holistic and effective and would be the single Meta framework for integrating and creditizing learning in various dimensions of academics, skilling and experiential learning including relevant experience and proficiency/ professional levels acquired, subject to assessment. The NCrF provides for creditization of all learning and assignment, accumulation, storage, transfer & redemption of credits, subject to assessment; removes distinction and establishes academic equivalence between vocational & general education while enabling mobility within & between them, and its operationalization through the Academic Bank of Credits (ABC).

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